

Development prospect of shallot from true shallot seed as planting material based on land suitability in Kampar regency, Riau province

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ABSTRACT

Productivity of shallot (Allium ascalonicum L.) in Riau Province does not supply domestic needs due to various factors including farmers still rely on the use of bulb as a source of seed. It is well known that in terms of production costs, disease resistance and shallot production, True Shallot Seed (TSS) has some advantages compared to bulb. The study was conducted in April 2018 in Kampar with descriptive analysis to determine the development prospect of TSS as planting material. This study used data from primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through direct interview to farmers in the field, while secondary data obtained from government publications, websites, books and journal articles. Kampar Regency as a lowland area with an altitude of 0 - 500 masl does not support shallot plants to produce TSS however the development of shallot area through TSS remains a concern of local government. The potential of shallot area for Kampar regency is 15,431 hectares or 8.48% from the total of all regencies/cities in Riau Province. After potential land suitability for the development of shallots in Riau Province, Kampar District is included in the category of conditionally suitable land that can be appropriate if the limiting factors have been fixed. It can be concluded that the use of TSS as a seed source with various advantages has prospects for further development in Kampar regency to increase the shallot productions.

Keywords : *Allium ascalonicum L.*, True Shallot Seed, Land Suitability

INTRODUCTION

Shallots (*Allium ascalonicum L.*) become a national strategic commodity because the production has not been evenly distributed throughout the year. As like as chili and garlic, shallots are categorized as important agricultural products controlling inflation. In the 2017 Performance Report of the Directorate General of Horticulture, the achievement of national shallot production performance is included in the successful category which is the result of special efforts such as growing production centers outside Java for regional or island independence and the development of seed with seed independence.

Based on Decree of the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 830/Kpts/RC.040/12/2016, Kampar and Pekanbaru are

location of horticultural commodity priority of shallot which developed in Riau Province. At present Riau Province has not been able to fulfill the needs of shallots independently which still depends on supply from Java, West Sumatera and North Sumatera. Since 2013, the Kampar District Government has launched a program to increase shallot production by pioneering the planting of shallots in Sei Geringging Village, Kampar Kiri District. The exceptional support from the central and regional governments of production facilities packages, technical development of cultivation and technology assistance from upstream to downstream has made the efforts of the district government of Kampar to be successful with productivity of 10 tons/ha and attracting the interest of farmers to cultivate shallots.

In previous research using seed bulb as planting material, the farmers in Sei Geringging in 2015 reported Gross revenue of shallot farming was IDR 490,000,000, while production costs amounted to IDR 321,258,734, then net income of shallot farming amounted to IDR 168,741,266 per 4 ha with RCR value amounted to 1.53 (Herlita et al. 2016). Another study in the same year found that the farming analysis showed the biggest cost in the cultivation of shallots was bulb seeds and labor. The high price of bulb due to the cost of long distance from the center of the seed causing high shipping costs (Yusuf and Swastika 2016). In addition, the risk of bulb damage during the expedition causes the amount of bulb needed is greater. The need of seeds in large quantities for bulb as planting material and relatively expensive price of tubers makes farmers use the bulb from previous yield (Basuki 2010). By reducing costs for seeds, it is expected that the farming carried out by shallot farmers will be more profitable. In addition, the use of quality seeds is also believed to be the beginning of a successful agricultural business because seeds are the basis for optimal plant growth and development. True shallot seed (TSS) is an alternative planting material of shallots with some advantages. It is well known that in terms of production costs, disease resistance and shallot production, TSS has some advantages compared to bulb. The information of TSS potential as planting material with the environmental suitability will convince farmers and the government to develop shallot cultivation in Kampar.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in April 2018 in Kampar with descriptive analysis. The data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Primary data collection was done by direct interview to the farmers in the field, while secondary data obtained from government publications, websites, books and journal articles. Primary data related to the numbers of yields, varieties

used, input cost, and constraint factors in shallot production. Data were obtained through interviews involving randomly chosen 20 shallot farmers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Aside from using bulbs and shoots, the production of shallot is also obtained from the planting of botanical seeds (Darma, 2015). Despite several potential advantages, including lower planting material costs, reduced transmission of seed-borne diseases, and higher yields, there has been very little adoption of true seed shallot.

The introduction of TSS as a source of seeds in Kampar District has begun in 2016 through mentoring activities to onion farmers by Riau AIAT using shallot seed of Tuk Tuk variety from East-West Seed Indonesia (EWINDO) seed companies and continued in 2017 using Trisula varieties produced by seed breeders fostered by North Sumatra AIAT also from the newly varieties released by EWINDO, Sanren and Lokananta. But it was not as easy as the introduction of planting with bulb in the early development of onion before, farmers were not directly interested in adopting cultivation technology using TSS. The addition of harvest time and production costs makes farmers reluctant to use seeds as planting material (Darma 2015) as well as transitional adaptation of cultivation techniques from the use of easy and practical bulb to seeds that require maintenance persistence, especially in the initial phase of growth (Bambang et al. 2015).

The seed bulb production from TSS can be done in three ways, namely planting TSS directly in the field (direct seedling), sowing TSS seeds first so that seedlings are produced and planting mini bulb (shallots sets) (Sumarni et al. 2012) Mini bulbs are small bulbs, which are 2–3 g in size produced as seed products produced by TSS propagation. Mini bulbs are produced by reducing the fertilizer dosage of plants and using scattered density / tight spacing (Bambang et al. 2015).

The difference in sowing media and TSS sowing method does not affect the weight of bulb and the number of bulb based on the size of bulbs produced. TSS sow quality factors seem to have more influence on the amount of TSS that grows than the sowing media and the way it sits (Sopha et al. 2015). Harvesting of mini tubers is carried out when plants aged 85 to 90 days after planting are adjusted to the physical conditions of the plants in the field. Plants are dismantled, cleaned and processed as seed tubers with a 2-month dormancy period, before they are ready to be replanted (Bambang et al. 2015). The use of seedling as planting material is thought to be more promising than through mini bulb. This is because the production of mini bulbs is still low, which is around 36% of the total weight of bulb (Sopha et al. 2015). In relatively fertile

soils, the age of the younger seed will accelerate the adaptation of the plant to the environment so that the growth and development of the plant is not inhibited. If the age of the seed is too old, the plant does not have enough time to complete its vegetative growth, the plant aging more quickly, entering the generative phase faster, and the results are not optimal. Older seed ages are expected to adapt more quickly to suboptimal land conditions (Sopha 2017).

The quality and characteristics of the land also determine the success of shallots development. The land quality includes temperature, water availability, oxygen availability, rooting media, nutrient retention, toxicity, sulfidic hazard and erosion hazard level. These factors are used in land suitability assessment for the development of a commodity. According to data from the Kampar District Regional Development Planning Agency (2016), the topography of Kampar Regency is largely a hilly area along the Bukit Barisan bordering West Sumatra Province with an altitude of 0 - 500 masl and a slope of 0 - 40%. The topography of the area is generally flat, sloping, to very steep. Formed from sedimentary rocks and meta sediments, metamorphic rocks, and breakthrough rocks that are scattered throughout the region. The western region towards the coast, formed from metamorphosis rock geological formations, sedimentary rocks, while the eastern region is formed from sedimentary rocks.

The physiography of the land of Kampar Regency is dominated by a group of peat domes, alluvial, plains, acid tuff plains, hills and mountains. In general, Kampar Regency has a tropical climate with an average air temperature of 27°C - 33°C, relative humidity between 78 - 94%, and an average rainfall of 2,830 millimeters per year. Some soil type with relatively fertile conditions is generally organosol, glei humus, alluvial, hydromorphic gray, yellow red podzolic, litosol and regosol. Organosol soil types are widespread in swampy lowlands and associated with humus, the farther from the riverbank the thicker the peat material is and is known as ombrogen peat.

The agricultural areas of Kampar Regency are grouped into areas of food crops, horticulture, plantations and livestock. Food crops were developed in Tapung Hilir Subdistrict, Bangkinang Seberang, East Kampar, Tambang, Perhentian Raja, Siak Hulu, Kampar Kiri, Gunung Sahilan, Bangkinang Barat, Salo, Kampar Utara, Kampar, Rumbio Jaya. While Horticulture was developed in the Districts of West Bangkinang, Bangkinang, Bangkinang Seberang, Gunung Sahilan, and Tambang.

In the Riau Province 1: 250,000 Scale Potential and Red Onion Regional Development Potential Map issued by the Ministry of Agriculture in 2017, there is no location in the category that is very suitable or conditional on the development of shallots in Kampar District, but 453,943 ha of land is classified as inappropriate. This means that the land in Kampar has a severe limiting

factor that is difficult to be improved due to high rainfall (> 3,000 mm / year) and slope > 15%. Riau Province has the potential to develop shallots on the medium category with 10.89% (181.920 Ha) in Sumatra and Kampar Regency in the third position after Rokan Hilir and Rokan Hulu at 8.48% (15.431 Ha). Kampar District is included in the category of conditionally suitable land that can be appropriate if the limiting factors have been fixed.

In high rainfall, the soil type of brown Latosol, association of Latosol - Andisol, and Andisol are more suitable for developing off-season shallot compared to Grumosol or Red Yellow Podsollic with heavy clay texture, because the land is better drained and easier to manage (Suwandi 2015). The dry land in Kampar Regency has the potential for shallots development but requires special attention and efforts, among others, in improving soil properties. Red yellow podzolic soil itself is a soil formed due to high rainfall so that fertility is relatively low due to leaching. Provision of nutrients for plants can be done by adding fertilizers both organic and inorganic. Through the addition of organic matter, the previously heavy soil becomes a relatively lighter crumb structure. Vertical movement of water or infiltration can be improved and the soil can absorb water faster so that surface flow and erosion are reduced.

Kampar Regency received funds from shallot production facilities from national budget of Ministry of Agriculture and Directorate General of Horticulture in 2018, namely 25 hectares of shallot development from tuber seeds in 12 subdistricts and 2 hectares of TSS seed seeds in Kualu Village, Tambang District. This TSS will be developed as a source of seeds to meet seed needs in Kampar District. Currently the variety used is Lokananta which is a seed product from EWINDO. From the results of interviews with farmers, information was obtained that farmers preferred the Bima variety which is the preference of shallots consumers in Riau. Consumers generally prefer bulbs that are bright red, medium size, have a strong and pungent taste. However, due to the limited availability of TSS, the choice of farmers to switch to Lokananta also has the advantage of being resistant to high rainfall and also very suitable for lowlands.

The stages of seeding TSS adopted by farmers include (1) Seed treatment with Fungicide Previcur N; (2) Preparation of media sowings soil : stabel manure : rice hull charcoal 1: 1: 1; (3) Sowing with a density of 50 gr / m² and covered with plastic for 4-5 days; (4) Arranging sunlight by using paranet or plastic lid; (5) Maintenance which includes watering, fertilizing with NPK 2 g/L of water at the age of 4 weeks after sowing and weeding (6) Preparation of transplanting to the land at 6-7 weeks after sowing with an acclimatization process for 1 week. This the method of seeding carried out is based on technical guidance on shallot cultivation by the agricultural extension officer.

For shallot planting on dry land during the rainy season, plants require medium textured soils, and are well drained. Planting shallots in acid soils which is pH <6 is highly recommended to be calcified first using agricultural lime or dolomite. For land with a soil pH <5.5, liming of about 1.5 tons / ha of or dolomite is needed and applied at the time of tillage at least 2 weeks before the onion is planted (Suwandi 2015).

Planting and maintaining plants on the land is the same as planting seeds from tubers. Harvesting of mini tubers is carried out when plants aged 85 to 90 days after planting are adjusted to the physical conditions of the plants in the field (Bambang et al. 2015). After that the seed process is carried out by drying in the field or in the room using instore drying. For commercial purposes, tuber seeds from TSS must go through a certification process by the Seed Monitoring and Certification Agency.

The focus of the shallot revitalization agribusiness in the future is to encourage the development of agribusiness based on resource abundance and unskilled labor, to capital-based agribusiness and skilled personnel, and driven by the application of location-specific technological innovations. With the development of shallot seed system innovation from TSS, it is expected that there will be some benefits such as the availability of alternative sources of quality shallot seeds easily, massively and sustainably, encouraging self-sufficiency of shallot seeds, opening up seed industry opportunities for seed breeders, and shallot productivity increases is expected to upgrade the farmers income (Rossliani 2015).

CONCLUSIONS

Shallot development in Riau province should consider potential land suitability. Kampar District is categorized as conditionally suitable land for appropriate shallot development if the limiting factors have been managed. the use of TSS as a seed source with various advantages has prospects for further development in Kampar regency to increase the shallot productions.

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